

Synthesis of 4-Imidazolyl-2-Methyl-5-Nitro-8-Hydroxy Quinolines as Possible Antiprotozoal Agents

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4-Chloro-2-methyl-5-nitro-8-hydroxy quinolines were condensed with imidazole and its derivatives to obtain 4-imidazolyl-2-methyl-5-nitro-8-hydroxy quinolines having no significant antiprotozoal activity.

OBSERVATION of antiprotozoal activity^{1,2} of metronidazole [1-(2-hydroxy-ethyl)-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole] and 5-nitro-8-hydroxy quinolines prompted us to synthesise compounds of the type (1) to examine their amebicidal and trichomonacidal activity. Such compounds possess both the features of 8-hydroxy quinoline and imidazole.

These compounds have been prepared by treating an appropriate 4-chloro quinoline with an imidazole derivative in presence of phenol. 2-Methyl-4-chloro-5-nitro-8-hydroxy quinolines have been prepared by demethylation of the corresponding 8-methoxy quinoline with 2 N NaOH. 4-Chloro-2-methyl-5-nitro quinolines and the corresponding 7-nitro isomers have been prepared by nitration of 2-methyl-4-chloro-8-methoxy quinoline with concentrated HNO₃ in H₂SO₄ medium which gave a dinitro derivative along with two mononitro compounds. The 5-nitro compound (m.p. 113-14°) has been separated out from the mixture of mononitro quinolines by fractional crystallisation. The structure of this nitro compound has been proved by the fact that dehalogenation and conversion of the nitro group to chloro gave chloro-2-methyl-8-methoxy quinoline which was found to be identical with that of an authentic sample of 5-chloro-2-methyl-8-methoxy quinoline. Similarly, 2-methyl-3-*n*-propyl-4-chloro-8-methoxy quinoline was nitrated to a mixture of dinitro and corresponding 5-nitro and 7-nitro quinolines. The dichloro compound, obtained on conversion of the 5-nitro compound, was found to be identical with an authentic sample of 2-methyl-3-*n*-propyl-4,5-dichloro-8-methoxy quinoline prepared in this laboratory³.

Biological activity: None of the compounds described in this paper was found to be significantly active *in vitro* against *E. histolytica*, *T. vaginalis* and *T. foetus* at a concentration of 12.5 mg/ml. An explanation of the absence of significant activity may be that the geometry of these molecules perhaps does not favourably fit with the geometry of the active site of the enzyme system of the microorganism involved in the interaction.

Experimental

2-Methyl-4-chloro-5-nitro-8-methoxy quinoline and 2-methyl-4-chloro-7-nitro-8-methoxy quinoline: Conc. HNO₃ (13 ml) was slowly added to an ice cooled and stirred solution of 2-methyl-4-chloro-8-methoxy quinoline (13 g) dissolved in conc. H₂SO₄ (32.5 ml) over half an hour. The solution was then poured on crushed ice under stirring. A yellow solid (1.5 g) separated out. It was collected by filtration, washed with dilute NH₄OH and crystallised from a large volume of ethyl alcohol to yield a dinitro derivative, m.p. >300° (decomp.). Found: N, 13.81. Calculated for C₁₁H₈N₂O₅Cl; N, 14.11%.

The filtrate was neutralised with NH₄OH and the separated yellow solid was collected by filtration. This solid (15 g) was a mixture of 5-nitro and 7-nitro derivatives which were separated by fractional crystallisation from aqueous ethyl alcohol (1:1) when the more soluble fraction was isolated, m.p. 113-14°; yield 9.4 g (60%). Found: C, 51.85; H, 3.17; N, 10.64. Calculated for C₁₁H₈N₂O₅Cl; C, 52.31; H, 3.56; N, 11.08%. The structure of the compound was proved to be 2-methyl-4-chloro-5-nitro-8-methoxy quinoline.

The residual mass was crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 150-51°; yield 1.56 g (10%). Found: C, 51.90; H, 3.27; N, 10.68. Calculated for C₁₁H₈N₂O₅Cl; C, 52.31; H, 3.56; N, 10.08%.

5-Amino-2-methyl-8-methoxy quinoline: 2-Methyl-4-chloro-5-nitro-8-methoxy quinoline (4 g) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (100 ml) and was hydrogenated at room temperature in presence of Pd/C (0.1 g). The catalyst was filtered off and the solvent removed from the filtrate. The residue was treated with dil. NH₄OH. The base was extracted

with ether, dry ethereal HCl was added to it when a solid was obtained. It was crystallised from a mixture of ethyl alcohol and ethyl acetate, m.p. 211-12°. Found: N, 10.81. Calculated for $C_{11}H_{14}N_2OCl_2$; N, 10.72%.

The above hydrochloride was dissolved in water and neutralised by liquor NH_3 when a light yellow solid was obtained. It was crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (60-80°) to a colourless compound, m.p. 148-49°; yield 90% (2.5 g). Found: C, 70.01; H, 6.18; N, 14.35. Calculated for $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O$; C, 70.20; H, 6.38; N, 14.8%.

2-Methyl-5-chloro-8-methoxy quinoline: 2-Methyl-5-amino-8-methoxy quinoline dihydrochloride (0.5 g) was dissolved in a mixture of conc. HCl (1 ml) and water (4 ml) and cooled to 0°. A solution of $NaNO_2$ (0.3 g) in water (1 ml) was added slowly to the above solution. A mixture of $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ (1 g), NaCl (0.5 g), copper turnings (0.5 g), conc. HCl (4 ml) and water (12.5 ml) was boiled until the solution was colourless. To this well cooled Cu_2Cl_2 solution was added slowly under stirring the cold diazotised solution, when the reaction proceeded with frothing. Stirring was continued for another 2 hr and the solution was left overnight. The solution was then filtered, washed, made alkaline with liquor NH_3 in cold when a solid separated out. The solid was filtered, washed and dried and purified further by crystallisation from petroleum ether (40-60°), m.p. 93°; yield 0.11 g (20%). Found: C, 63.21; H, 4.35; N, 6.5. Calculated for $C_{11}H_{10}NOCl$; C, 63.61; H, 4.81; N, 6.74%. It was found to be identical with an authentic sample of 2-methyl-5-chloro-8-methoxy quinoline (m.p. 93°)³.

2-Methyl-4-chloro-5-nitro-8-hydroxy quinoline: 2-Methyl-4-chloro-5-nitro-8-methoxy quinoline (3 g) was refluxed with 2 N NaOH (300 ml) for 4 hr⁴. The solution was then acidified with AcOH when a yellow solid separated out. It was collected by filtration, dried and then heated with $POCl_3$ (50 ml) in an oil bath for half an hour at 120-130°. Subsequent pouring in ice-water and basification with liquor NH_3 yielded a yellow solid which crystallised as needles from petroleum ether, m.p. 160-61°; yield 2 g (70%). ir (KBr) 3350 cm^{-1} (OH). Found: C, 50.2; H, 2.45; N, 11.52. Calculated for $C_{10}H_7O_3N_2Cl$; C, 50.3; H, 2.93; N, 11.73%.

2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-5-nitro quinoline and 2-methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-7-nitro quinoline: 2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-8-methoxy quinoline (5 g) was dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid (12.5 ml). The solution was cooled in ice and conc. HNO_3 (5 ml) was added to it with stirring over half an hour. Stirring was continued for another hour and the resultant mixture added to crushed ice. A yellow solid (0.3 g) separated out which was filtered, washed with dilute NH_4OH and crystallised from large volume of ethyl alcohol, to yield a dinitro derivative m.p. > 300° (decomp.). Found: N, 12.12. Calculated for $C_{14}H_{14}O_2N_2Cl$; N, 12.37%.

The filtrate was then neutralised with dilute NH_4OH and was made alkaline to phenolphthalein. A yellow solid separated out and was collected by filtration. The solid (5.5 g) was a mixture of 5-nitro and 7-nitro derivatives. They were separated by fractional crystallisation from aqueous ethyl alcohol (1:1), whereby the more soluble fraction, m.p. 136-37° was isolated; yield 1.8 g (30%). Found: C, 56.58; H, 5.1; N, 9.53. Calculated for $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2Cl$; C, 57.04; H, 5.09; N, 9.5%. The structure of the compound was proved to be 2-methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-5-nitro-8-methoxy quinoline.

The residual mass was crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 214-15°; yield 3.5 g (59%). Found: C, 57.00; H, 4.59; N, 9.05. Calculated for $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2Cl$; C, 57.04; H, 5.09; N, 9.5%. The compound was probably 2-methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-7-nitro-8-methoxy quinoline.

2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-5-amino-8-methoxy quinoline: A mixture of 2-methyl-4-chloro-5-nitro-8-methoxy quinoline (1.4 g), conc. HCl (15 ml) and $SnCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (5.64 g) was refluxed in an oil bath for 4 hr. A clear solution formed at first but finally solids separated out. The contents were dissolved in water (100 ml) and H_2S gas was passed through the solution until complete precipitation of tin was effected. The tin sulphides were removed by filtration and the filtrate was boiled to remove H_2S . The solution was cooled and made alkaline with liquor NH_3 . The separated solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from a mixture of benzene-petroleum ether (60-80°) (1:1) in yellow needles, m.p. 92-93°; yield 1.18 g (90%). Found: C, 63.25; H, 5.95; N, 10.1. Calculated for $C_{14}H_{17}N_2OCl$; C, 63.5; H, 6.4; N, 10.5%.

2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-4,5-dichloro-8-methoxy quinoline: 2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-5-amino-4-chloro-8-methoxy quinoline (1.3 g) was diazotised and treated with Cu_2Cl_2 in the usual manner. The product was purified by chromatographic method over silica gel using petroleum ether (40-60°) as an eluent, yield 0.35 g (25%). Found: C, 58.71; H, 5.1; N, 4.63. Calculated for $C_{14}H_{15}NCl_2O$; C, 59.1; H, 5.2; N, 4.9%.

2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-4-hydroxy-5-chloro-8-methoxy quinoline: A mixture of 5-chloro-*o*-anisidine (15 g) and ethyl *n*-propyl acetoacetate (18 g) was treated with a few drops of dilute (1:1) HCl and the mixture kept overnight. Dry benzene (100 ml) was then added to it and the mixture heated in an oil bath at 130-140° in a Dean-Stark apparatus till no more water collected. Benzene was removed by distillation. The residual viscous mass was poured dropwise into boiling diphenyl oxide (500 ml) and boiled for 15 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and diluted with petroleum ether (60-80°). The separated solid was filtered and crystallised from dilute ethyl alcohol, m.p. 215-16°; yield 10 g (39%).

2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-4,5-dichloro-8-methoxy quinoline: The above 4-hydroxy quinoline (10 g) was

heated under reflux with a mixture of POCl_3 (21 ml) and PCl_5 (1.8 g) in an oil bath^a at 130-133° for 5-6 hr. The product was cooled, decomposed with ice, made alkaline with NH_4OH . The precipitated solid was filtered, thoroughly washed with water and crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (60-80°) (1:1), m.p. 107-108°; yield 7 g (65%). Found: C, 58.75; H, 5.1; N, 4.52. Calculated for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{ONCl}_2$; C, 59.1; H, 5.2; N, 4.9%.

2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-5-nitro-8-hydroxy quinoline: 2-Methyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-5-nitro-8-methoxy quinoline (1.25 g) was refluxed with 2 N NaOH (125 ml) for 24 hr^a. The solution was acidified with AcOH when a yellow solid separated which was filtered, dried and refluxed with POCl_3 (25 ml) in an oil bath for half an hour at 120-130°. Finally, the mass was poured in ice-water and made alkaline with liquor NH_3 . The product was treated with charcoal when a yellow solid (0.5 g) separated; yield 0.5 g (48%). It crystallised in needles from petroleum ether (60-80°), m.p. 124-25°, ir (KBr) 3375 cm^{-1} (OH). Found: C, 55.25; H, 4.25; N, 9.5. Calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$; C, 55.65; H, 4.63; N, 9.88%.

General method for preparing 4-imidazolyl-2-methyl-5-nitro-8-hydroxy quinolines: A mixture of 4-chloroquinoline derivatives (0.005 mole), imidazole or its derivatives^a (0.005 mole) and phenol (4 ml) was refluxed in an oil bath for 24 hr at about 200°. It was then acidified with dil. HCl and extracted with ether to remove phenol. Aqueous HCl was separated out and it was made alkaline with liquor NH_3 when a solid separated. The solid was collected by filtration, washed with water, dried and crystallised from a suitable solvent.

Using this method the following compounds were prepared:

- $\text{I}(\text{X}=\text{Y}=\text{R}=\text{H})$, m.p. 102-103°^a. Yield 40%
 $\text{I}(\text{X}=\text{R}=\text{H}; \text{Y}=\text{NO}_2)$ m.p. 85-86°^b. Yield 40%
 $\text{I}(\text{X}=\text{Me}; \text{Y}=\text{R}=\text{H})$, m.p. 98-99°^b. Yield 45%
 $\text{I}(\text{X}=\text{Me}; \text{Y}=\text{NO}_2; \text{R}=\text{H})$, m.p. 129-30°^b. Yield 40%
 $\text{I}(\text{X}=\text{Y}=\text{H}; \text{R}=\text{n-C}_3\text{H}_7)$, m.p. 101-102°^b. Yield 36%

(a) Crystallised from aqueous ethanol; (b) crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (60-80°) (1:1) in yellow needles and gave satisfactory C, H, N analyses.

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References

1. R. CAVIER, J. SAEVÉL and P. BUOT, *Ann. Pharm. France*, 1964, 22, 281.
2. H. PARNEMAUN and H. LIEBIG, (Risdell-de-Haen-A. G.), *Ger. Offen.*, 1970, 1, 812, 061; *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, 66, 66457t.
3. M. WEIZMANN and E. BOGRACHOV, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1222.
4. F. BORDIN and O. ANTONELLO, *Ann. Chim. (Rome)*, 1967, 57, 917.
5. K. L. PATHAK and B. PATHAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 37, 281.
6. R. G. FARGHER and F. L. PYMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 217.